

RTBV. Those that gave negative transmission were identified as plants infected with RTBV alone.

Plants infected with RTSV alone were identified next. Virus-free leafhoppers were given 24 h access to each healthy-looking plant inoculated with RTSV alone, followed by an 8 h or overnight acquisition access to previously identified RTBV-infected plants. The insects were then used to inoculate 7-d-old TN1 seedlings as above. Plants that gave posi-

tive transmission were identified as RTSV-infected while those that gave negative transmission were identified as healthy plants.

In this experiment, TN1 seedlings were inoculated with tungro using plants infected with both virus particles. Sixteen inoculated plants with moderate stunting and discoloration were tested: 2 plants had both RTBV and RTSV and 14 had RTBV alone. Fourteen symptomless plants inoculated with RTSV done were

used for RTSV detection: 12 plants had RTSV and 2 were healthy.

To test the accuracy of this method, the virus particles present in each plant were counterchecked serologically with a latex test. Results of the serological test showed that the method was accurate.

This method takes about 10 d to detect RTBV-infected plants and another 10 d to detect RTSV. In contrast, results by serology and electron microscopy are obtained in only a few hours. □

Quality of rice grains from sheath rot-affected plants

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Sheath rot caused by *Acrocyndrium* (= *Sarocladium*) *oryzae* Sawada is a major rice disease in India. We recorded changes in grain quality caused by the disease.

Trials with ADT31 and ADT36, both popular varieties in Tamil Nadu, were conducted during 1982 kuruvai. The disease intensity was arbitrarily classified into 5 grades (0, 3, 5, 7, 9) based upon the lesions on the leaf sheath near the panicle. 0 indicated no infection; 9 indicated the boot leaf sheath was completely infected and the panicle could not emerge. No grains formed in plants scoring 9.

Rice grains were harvested from individual plants with various disease intensity levels. Grains also were collected from

Changes in rice grain quality due to sheath rot incidence in 2 rice cultivars.

Disease intensity grade	Discolored grains				1000-grain wt (g)		Seed germination (%)		Protein content (%) of ADT36
	no./panicle		%panicle						
	ADT31	ADT36	ADT31	ADT36	ADT31	ADT36	ADT31	ADT36	
0	1	2	0.9	1.4	15.7	15.7	94	97	8.0
3	19	54	18.1	38.3	12.3	15.3	89	92	7.5
5	60	78	66.7	67.8	6.3	11.5	76	81	4.4
7	85	94	97.7	93.1	4.9	8.7	58	63	2.2
9	^a								

^aNo grains were formed.

healthy plants. One hundred panicles were collected for each disease intensity category.

Discolored and healthy grains from each panicle were counted. The 1,000-grain weight was measured by taking 4 samples in each category. Germination of seeds from each category was assessed by using the roll towel method and 400 seeds for each infection level. Protein content of ADT36 grains was assessed by estimating total nitrogen content by the micro-Kjeldahl method and multiplying it by 6.25. Two independent experiments, each with four replications, were conducted.

Disease of the boot leaf sheath caused discolored grains (see table). Although many different causes of grain discoloration have been reported, this is the first time that *Acrocyndrium oryzae* has been reported as a cause. Attempts to isolate the fungus from the discolored grains failed, which suggests that the fungus causes grain discoloration by inducing a physiological change.

The disease reduced the 1,000-grain weight and caused poor grain filling, which reduced seed germination (see table). Protein content of the grains was also affected. □

Leaf scald disease of rice in Karnataka, India

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Leaf scald disease of rice caused by *Rhynchosporium oryzae* was observed for the first time in Karnataka in Oct 1982 on Intan rice. Intan was very susceptible to the disease and had lesions covering more than 50% of the leaf area. Seed

Table 1. Incidence of *Rhynchosporium oryzae* on seeds from Karnataka State districts, India (400 seeds tested per sample following blotter method).

District	Samples tested (no.)	Infected samples (no.)	Samples (no.) at given range (%) of infection						
			0.5-5	6-10	11-20	21-30	31-40	41-50	51-64
Belgaum	2	2	2	—	—	—	—	—	—
Bellari	1	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Chikmagalur	3	1	—	—	—	—	1	—	—
Chitradurga	4	3	2	—	1	—	—	—	—
Dharwar	5	1	—	—	1	—	—	—	—
Hassan	7	4	3	1	—	—	—	—	—
Kodagu	5	5	—	—	2	—	1	1	1
Mandya	3	2	2	—	—	—	—	—	—
Mysore	20	19	9	7	1	2	—	—	—
Total	50	31	18	8	5	2	2	1	1